

PREVALENCE OF DEPRESSION, ANXIETY AND STRESS AND ITS RISK FACTOR AMONG ACADEMIC STUDENTS

Sadia Batool^{*1}, Erum Bibi², Fatima Ashiq³, Muhammad Danish⁴, Syda Wajhiah Rizvi⁵

^{*1,5}Department of Medical Laboratory Technology, Khwaja Fareed Campus, The Islamia University of Bahawalpur

²Department of Nursing (ICU), Choudhry Pervaiz Elahi Institute of Cardiology Multan, Punjab Pakistan

^{3,4}Department of Cardiology, Shahida Islam Teaching Hospital, Bahawalpur Road, 100M Lodhran, Punjab, Pakistan

¹sadiabatool1155@gmail.com, ²eshalsial039@gmail.com, ³ashiqfatima1@gmail.com, ⁴hmdanishaltaf2000@gmail.com, ⁵wajhiah.rizvi@iub.edu.pk

Corresponding Author: *

Sadia Batool

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18053502>

Received	Accepted	Published
27 October 2025	11 December 2025	25 December 2025

ABSTRACT

Objective: To assess the prevalence and incidences of stress, anxiety, and depression among university students at The Islamia University of Bahawalpur and to determine the socio-demographic characteristics.

Methodology: This descriptive cross-sectional research included participants from five different faculties at the Khawaja Fareed Campus, Islamia University of Bahawalpur. About 300 students agreed to participate, but analysis was carried out on 249 students aged 18-24 years who provided complete data. Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS v19. Chi-square analysis and multivariate logistic regression were employed to examine associations and identify significant predictors, considering a p-value of less than 0.05 as statistically significant.

Results: Psychological distress was highly prevalent: depression (76.3%), anxiety (81.9%), and stress (60.6%). Moderate depression (36.9%) and extremely severe anxiety (33.3%) were common. Stress was mostly moderate (24.5%). Multivariate regression analysis revealed no statistically significant predictors for depression; however, smoking (OR = 5.76, p = 0.115) and living arrangement (OR = 1.24, p = 0.098) exhibited trends toward significance. Anxiety was significantly predicted by place of birth (OR = 0.68, p = 0.041), living arrangement (OR = 1.37, p = 0.033), and parental education (OR = 1.22, p = 0.027). Stress was significantly associated with living arrangement (OR = 1.30, p = 0.044) and age group (OR = 0.55, p = 0.025).

Conclusion: There is an alarmingly high prevalence of mental health issues among university students, strongly linked to academic pressure, socio-demographic variables, and lifestyle factors. Educational institutions must implement mental health support systems, counseling services, and awareness programs to address this growing concern.

Keywords: Emotional distress, psychological symptoms, Depression Anxiety Stress Scales (DASS-21), Higher education students, Demographic characteristics, Mental well-being

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Mental health is defined as a person's ability to

manage emotions, cope with stress, and function psychologically, with impairment affecting cognitive and social functioning, work efficiency,

and daily life [1]. The World Health Organization (WHO) describes mental health as a state of well-being in which individuals realize their potential, cope with life stressors, and contribute to their community; thus, it is not merely the absence of mental illness [2]. Globally, one in four adolescents aged 12-24 experiences mental health disorders, including depression and schizophrenia, yet this population remains underserved, particularly university students who are at risk for depression, anxiety, suicidal behavior, and non-suicidal self-injury [3,4]. Poor mental health among students is linked to diminished academic performance, quality of life, and overall health [5]. In developing countries such as Pakistan, limited research, awareness, and institutional support exacerbate these challenges, resulting in mood disorders, academic difficulties, substance misuse, and suicidal behavior [6,7]. Students with untreated psychological disorders often exhibit lower GPAs and higher dropout rates [8,9]. Stress, lack of coping mechanisms, and inadequate support systems further contribute to poor academic adjustment, social isolation, low self-esteem, and sleep disturbances [10,11]. In 2019, 970 million people globally lived with a mental disorder, including 301 million with anxiety and 280 million with depression, numbers that increased during the COVID-19 pandemic by 26% and 28%, respectively [12,13]. Among medical students, depression prevalence ranges from 10.4-60% and anxiety from 29.4-69% [14]. International studies report moderate to severe depression, anxiety, and stress among university students in Hong Kong (27%) [15], India (depression 18.5%, anxiety 24.4%, stress 20%) [16], and Malaysia (depression 13.9-29.3%, anxiety 51.5-55%, stress 12.9-21.6%) [17,18].

1.2 Depression

Depression is highly prevalent among university students undergoing the critical transition from adolescence to adulthood, with pressures related to social integration, academic success, and future planning contributing to stress and anxiety [19]. The average age of depression onset is decreasing [20], and over two-thirds of young adults do not seek help [21]. Depression is a mood disorder characterized by persistent low mood, emotional distress, irritability, cognitive decline, social withdrawal, loss of motivation, anhedonia, hopelessness, hypotonia, and in severe cases,

delusions [22,23]. It is a leading cause of global disability, with lifetime prevalence of 20-25% in women and 7-12% in men, accounting for 50% of psychiatric consultations and 12% of hospital admissions [24].

1.3 Anxiety

Anxiety is an uncontrollable, persistent, unpleasant emotional state often accompanied by physiological tension and anticipatory fear. It is increasingly prevalent due to social and environmental pressures and can lead to functional impairments if severe or prolonged [25,26].

1.4 Stress

Stress is a universal phenomenon arising from internal and external sources, leading to worry, emotional exhaustion, fatigue, and potential psychological disorders, including PTSD [27-30]. High stress in adolescents contributes to depression, anxiety, suicide, substance use, and antisocial behavior [4,31], with impacts on immunity, chronic disease, cognition, coping, and social outcomes [32].

1.5 Risk Factors for Stress, Anxiety, and Depression (SAD)

SAD is influenced by multiple biopsychosocial factors across six domains:

Psychological: Low self-esteem, high neuroticism, low extraversion, loneliness, relocation, pre-existing mental health conditions, PTSD, and childhood exposure to violence increase SAD risk [33-37].

Academic: Rigorous programs (medicine, nursing), workload, emotional sensitivity, fieldwork, lack of preparedness, poor academic performance, year of study, and unsupportive faculty-student relationships elevate SAD [35,38-46].

Biological: Chronic illness, disabilities, gender differences (higher in females), age variations, and societal stigma affecting help-seeking contribute to SAD [42,44,47-52].

Lifestyle: Alcohol and tobacco use, poor diet, physical inactivity, inadequate sleep, and poor time management are significant contributors [35,39,44,53-57,60].

Social: Family and peer support, romantic relationships, social participation, social media

use, minority status, and stigma influence SAD development [38,43,44,48,61-67].

Economic: Low household income, childhood poverty, part-time employment, workplace relationships, and financial stress among international students affect mental health [33,61,68-71].

Objective of the Study

To evaluate the prevalence and severity of anxiety, depression, and stress among students at The Islamia University of Bahawalpur (IUB) and examine associations with socio-demographic, academic, and lifestyle factors, providing evidence for targeted mental health interventions.

Significance and Rationale

The study provides regional insight into student mental health, informs university health services and policy, and highlights the impact of psychological factors on academic performance.

Problem Statement

University students face academic, social, and personal challenges that may lead to depression, anxiety, and stress. In Pakistan, the lack of comprehensive data limits effective support mechanisms. This study addresses the gap by assessing prevalence, severity, and associated factors of SAD among IUB students.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- i. What is the prevalence of anxiety, depression, and stress among IUB students?
- ii. How severe are these symptoms?
- iii. Which socio-demographic, academic, and lifestyle factors are associated with SAD?
- iv. What interventions do students perceive as necessary?

2. METHODOLOGY

This cross-sectional study was conducted among students at The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, with participants selected from five departments at the Khawaja Fareed Campus. Although about 300 students agreed to participate, analysis was carried out on 249 students who provided complete data. Prior ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee of the MLT Department, and faculties within the selected departments were chosen randomly, with a defined number of students recruited from each department. Inclusion criteria comprised students

aged 18-24 years, enrolled full-time or part-time, willing to participate with informed consent, capable of understanding and communicating in the study language, and available to complete the survey. Exclusion criteria included diagnosed mental health disorders under treatment, non-student individuals, and participants with incomplete survey data. Data were collected using a questionnaire initially designed in English and translated into Urdu, capturing socio-demographic and familial characteristics such as age, gender, academic department, semester, family income, parental marital status, place of birth, type of residence, parental education, smoking and alcohol use, and current living arrangements. Mental health assessment was performed using the 21-item Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS-21), which measures core emotional states of depression, anxiety, and stress, with each subscale containing seven items. Participants rated the frequency of symptoms over the past week on a 4-point Likert scale (0-3), and scores were doubled to match the 42-item DASS scoring system, producing a range of 0-42 for each subscale, where higher scores indicate greater emotional distress. Severity levels were categorized for depression (0-9 normal, 10-13 mild, 14-20 moderate, 21-27 severe, ≥ 28 extremely severe), anxiety (0-7 normal, 8-9 mild, 10-14 moderate, 15-19 severe, ≥ 20 extremely severe), and stress (0-13 normal, 14-18 mild, 19-25 moderate, 26-33 severe, ≥ 34 extremely severe). Data analysis was performed using IBM SPSS version 19.0, following thorough data cleaning. Descriptive statistics summarized categorical variables in frequencies and percentages, while outcome variables (depression, anxiety, and stress scores) were reported as means and standard deviations. Associations between categorical independent variables and mental health outcomes were evaluated using Chi-square tests, and multivariate regression analyses were conducted to identify significant predictors while controlling for confounders, with a p-value < 0.05 considered statistically significant.

LITERATURE REVIEW

3. Miron et al. (2019) studied 4,301 students in Spain using PSS-10, GAD-7, and PHQ-9, finding high levels of stress (50.2% anxiety, 47.18% depression), especially among women,

highlighting the need for targeted mental health interventions [72].

4. Othman et al. (2019) assessed 148 Canadian students, reporting 39.5% depression, 23.8% anxiety, and 80.3% stress. Academic, social, and socio-environmental factors influenced outcomes, underscoring multifactorial mental health determinants [73].

5. Wahed et al. (2017) surveyed 442 Egyptian medical students; 62.4% had stress, 64.3% anxiety, 60.8% depression, with higher rates in females and older students, highlighting the academic burden on mental health [74].

6. Beiter et al. (2015) found in 374 US undergraduates that stressors like academics and future uncertainty led to 11% severe stress, 15% severe anxiety, and 11% severe depression, emphasizing the need for student-centered support [75].

7. Amir Hamzah et al. (2019) reported 21% depression, 50% anxiety, and 12% stress among Malaysian first-year students, influenced by living arrangements, medical history, and regional differences [76].

8. Bayram et al. (2008) found in 1,617 Turkish students that 27.1% had depression, 47.1% anxiety, and 27% stress, with higher levels among females and lower-year students [77].

9. Teh et al. (2015) noted in 397 Malaysian students that medical students had higher distress, with 30.7% anxiety, 55.5% depression, and 16.6% stress, influenced by social and economic factors [78].

10. Asif et al. (2020) surveyed 500 Pakistani students; 75% reported depression, 88.4% anxiety, and 84.4% stress, highlighting urgent mental health concerns [79].

11. Ramón-Arbués et al. (2020) reported 18.4% depression, 23.6% anxiety, and 34.5% stress in 1,074 students, associated with lifestyle factors, self-esteem, and relationships [80].

12. Fauzi et al. (2021) found among 449 health sciences students that 65% had stress, 85.1% anxiety, 51.4% depression; academic progression, sleep quality, and fatigue were key factors [81].

13. Blanco et al. (2021) reported in 871 female students that 18.1% had severe depression, 22.8% severe anxiety, and 13.5% severe stress; personality traits influenced risk [82].

14. Hossain et al. (2022) found mild-to-moderate stress but over 40% severe anxiety among 351 Bangladeshi students, with gender and residence influencing outcomes [83].

15. Gabal et al. (2022) noted 64.2% depression, 77.1% anxiety, and 70.4% stress among 240 Egyptian medical students, influenced by BMI, screen use, and physical activity [84].

16. Yu et al. (2022) surveyed 6,032 Chinese students; 62.2% had no complaints, but anxiety co-occurred with depression; senior year, injuries, and lifestyle affected mental health [85].

17. Karing et al. (2021) reported in 2,548 German students during COVID-19 that 35.9% had depression, 27.7% anxiety, 25.1% stress; mindfulness was protective, while pandemic stressors were risks [86].

18. Shamsuddin et al. (2013) found among 506 Malaysian students moderate-to-severe depression (27.5%), anxiety (34%), and stress (18.6%), higher among older students, females, and rural backgrounds [87].

Summary: Across global studies, university students consistently show high prevalence of stress, anxiety, and depression, influenced by gender, academic pressure, lifestyle, socio-environmental factors, and personality traits. These findings highlight the urgent need for targeted mental health support and preventive interventions in academic settings.

RESULTS

4.1 Descriptive Analysis of Socio-Demographic Variables and Risk Factors

Table 4.1: Frequency of Gender among University Students (N=249)

Gender	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Female	141	56.6
Male	108	43.4
Total	249	100

Explanation:

The female participants slightly outnumbered males, representing 56.6% of the sample, while males comprised 43.4%. This indicates a fairly balanced gender representation among students.

Table 4.2: Frequency of Age Groups among University Students (N=249)

Age Group	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
18-19	76	30.5
20-22	150	60.2
23-24	19	7.6
>24	4	1.6
Mean ± SD	20.46 ± 1.77	
Total	249	100

Explanation:

Most students (60.2%) were aged 20–22 years, followed by 18–19 years (30.5%). Older students (>24 years) were rare (1.6%).

Table 4.3: Department-wise Distribution (N=249)

Department	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Biochemistry	14	5.6
DPT	77	30.9
HND	7	2.8
MLT	123	49.4
Pharm D	28	11.2
Total	249	100

Explanation:

Medical Laboratory Technology (MLT) students formed the largest group (49.4%), followed by DPT (30.9%). Other departments had smaller representations.

Table 4.4: Semester-wise Distribution (N=249)

Semester	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
2nd	71	28.5
4th	56	22.5
6th	43	17.3
8th	67	26.9
10th	7	2.8
3rd	1	0.4
7th	4	1.6
Total	249	100

Explanation:

The highest number of students were in the 2nd and 8th semesters. The fewest were in the 3rd, 7th, and 10th semesters.

Table 4.5: Satisfaction with Own Education (N=249)

Satisfaction	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Yes	194	77.9
No	55	22.1
Total	249	100

Explanation:

Most students (77.9%) were satisfied with their education, while 22.1% reported dissatisfaction.

Table 4.6: Family Monthly Income Distribution (N=249)

Family Monthly Income	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Low (<50,000 PKR)	68	27.3
Middle (50,000-100,000 PKR)	132	53
High (>100,000 PKR)	0	0
Unknown	49	19.7
Total	249	100

Explanation:

Most families had middle-income levels (53%), followed by low income (27.3%). No high-income families were reported.

Table 4.7: Parents' Marital Status (N=249)

Parents' Marital Status	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Married	239	96
Separated/Divorced/Widowed	7	2.8
Unknown/Never Married	3	1.2
Total	249	100

Explanation:

The majority of students had married parents (96%), while a few were from separated, widowed, or unknown marital status families.

Table 4.8: Place of Birth Distribution (N=249)

Place of Birth	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Rural	79	31.7
Semi-Urban	69	27.7
Urban	101	40.6
Total	249	100

Explanation:

Urban-born students formed the largest group (40.6%), followed by rural (31.7%) and semi-urban (27.7%).

Table 4.9: Types of Accommodation (N=249)

Accommodation Type	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Flat/Apartment	111	44.6
Terrace/Semi-detached/Bungalow	75	30.1
Squatter/Others/Unknown	63	25.3
Total	249	100

Explanation:

Flats/apartments were the most common living arrangement (44.6%), followed by terraces (30.1%).

Table 4.10: Living Arrangements (N=249)

Living Arrangement	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
With Family	117	46.99
With Friends/Hostels	122	48.99
Alone/Others/Unknown	10	4.01
Total	249	100

Explanation:

Nearly half the students lived with friends or in hostels (48.99%), with 46.99% living with family.

Table 4.11: Parents' Education Level (N=249)

Parents Education	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Secondary	93	37.3
Graduation	71	28.5
Primary to Middle	56	22.5
Post-Graduation	28	11.2
Primary	1	0.4
Total	249	100

Explanation:

Most parents had secondary education (37.3%), followed by graduation (28.5%) and post-graduation (11.2%).

Table 4.12: Participation in Extracurricular Activities (N=249)

Participation	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Yes	133	53.4
No	116	46.6
Total	249	100

Explanation:

Slightly more than half of the students participated in extracurricular activities.

Table 4.13–4.15: Prevalence of Lifestyle Factors

Smoking:

Smoking	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Yes	10	4
No	239	96

Alcohol Consumption:

Alcohol	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Yes	3	1.2
No	246	98.8

Explanation:

Most students were non-smokers (96%) and abstained from alcohol (98.8%).

Table 4.16–4.17: Prevalence of Depression, Anxiety, and Stress

Mental Health	Normal (%)	Mild (%)	Moderate (%)	Severe (%)	Extremely Severe (%)
Depression	23.7	22.5	36.9	12.9	4
Anxiety	18.1	8.8	24.9	14.9	33.3
Stress	39.4	19.3	24.5	12.4	4.4

Explanation:

Moderate depression was the most common (36.9%).

Extremely severe anxiety was the highest among anxiety levels (33.3%).

Most students experienced normal stress (39.4%).

4.2 Chi-Square Analysis: Associations with Depression

Significant associations:

Semester of Study ($P = 0.005$): Students in 2nd, 4th, and 8th semesters had higher depression levels.

Satisfaction with Education ($P = 0.006$): Dissatisfied students had higher depression.

Alcohol Consumption ($P = 0.001$): Alcohol consumers showed higher depression severity.

Non-significant associations ($P > 0.05$):

Gender, age, department, family income, parents' marital status, place of birth, type of accommodation, living arrangement, parents' education, extracurricular participation, smoking.

4.3 Chi-Square Analysis: Associations with Anxiety

Significant association:

Department of Study ($P = 0.027$): Certain departments (Biochemistry) showed higher anxiety.

Non-significant associations ($P > 0.05$):

Gender, age, semester, satisfaction with education, family income, parents' marital status, place of birth, accommodation, living arrangement, parents' education, extracurricular activities, smoking, alcohol.

4.4 Chi-Square Analysis: Associations with Stress

Significant associations:

Age Group ($P = 0.044$): 18–19 age group had higher moderate stress.

Semester ($P = 0.003$): 2nd and 4th semesters showed higher stress.

Alcohol Consumption ($P = 0.000$): Students consuming alcohol experienced higher stress.

Non-significant associations ($P > 0.05$):

Gender, department, satisfaction with education, family income, parents' marital status, place of birth, accommodation, living arrangement, parents' education, extracurricular participation, smoking.

Summary of Key Findings:

Academic factors (semester, department) are significantly linked to depression and anxiety.

Personal factors (satisfaction with education, alcohol use) significantly influence depression and stress.

Gender, parental education, accommodation, and smoking were not significant predictors of mental health outcomes.

Moderate depression and extremely severe anxiety were the most prevalent mental health issues among students.

DISCUSSION

The present study sought to evaluate the prevalence and intensity of anxiety, depression & stress among university students, along with analyzing their average scores and age distribution. The results indicate a notably high level of psychological distress among the respondents, aligning with trends reported in both national and global literature.

The average scores for anxiety, depression & stress observed in this study were 14.14 ± 7.16 , 14.59 ± 7.47 , and 17.41 ± 8.12 , respectively. The mean age of the participants was 20.46 ± 1.77 years, indicating that the majority of respondents were young adults a demographic frequently identified as being at heightened risk for mental health challenges due to academic demands and the psychosocial adjustments associated with the transition to adulthood.

Regarding prevalence, 76.3% of students experienced some level of depression, 81.9% reported anxiety symptoms, and 60.6% suffered from stress. These rates are high and reflect serious mental health concerns within the student

population. Notably, the prevalence of anxiety (81.9%) was the highest, followed by depression and stress

The majority of participants reported moderate levels of depression (36.9%), while a considerable number experienced severe (12.9%) or extremely severe (4%) depression. Depression severity was significantly associated with semester of study ($p = 0.005$), educational satisfaction ($p = 0.006$), and alcohol consumption ($p = 0.001$). Students in certain semesters likely due to academic overload reported greater depressive symptoms, a finding supported by Sani et al. (2012) and Kulsoom & Afsar (2015). Dissatisfaction with one's academic experience also contributed significantly to depressive symptoms, highlighting the impact of unmet educational expectations on mental health. Alcohol use, while reported by a small number of students, was strongly associated with higher depression levels. This finding aligns with research suggesting alcohol can exacerbate depressive symptoms or serve as a maladaptive coping strategy (Quek et al., 2019). However, multivariate logistic regression found no variable to be a statistically significant independent predictor of depression, although smoking ($OR = 5.755$, $p = 0.115$) and living arrangement ($OR = 1.240$, $p = 0.098$) showed trends toward significance. This suggests a possible influence of these variables, warranting further research with larger samples.

Anxiety was the most prevalent disorder, with 33.3% experiencing extremely severe symptoms. Bivariate analysis showed a significant association with semester of study, educational satisfaction, and alcohol use (all $p < 0.05$). These trends mirror the findings for depression and further point to academic and behavioral stressors as key contributors. Multivariate regression identified place of birth ($p = 0.041$), living arrangement ($p = 0.033$), and parental education ($p = 0.027$) as statistically significant predictors of anxiety. Students born in certain areas had lower odds of anxiety, suggesting that background or familiarity with the university environment may play a protective role. Higher parental education was unexpectedly linked to higher anxiety, possibly reflecting increased familial expectations, which can heighten academic pressure (Amr et al., 2008; Puthran et al., 2016).

Moderate stress was most common (24.5%), with 60.6% of students reporting some level of stress.

Bivariate analysis revealed significant associations with age group ($p = 0.044$), semester of study ($p = 0.003$), and alcohol consumption ($p = 0.000$). Younger students (especially 18-19 years) reported higher stress, likely due to limited coping mechanisms and difficulty adjusting to academic demands. As with depression and anxiety, students in 2nd and 4th semesters were particularly affected, likely due to cumulative workload or key examinations. Multivariate regression confirmed that age group ($p = 0.025$) and living arrangement ($p = 0.044$) were significant predictors of stress. Older students exhibited significantly lower odds of stress, reinforcing the role of maturity and adaptive resilience in managing academic and social pressures. The influence of living arrangement across all three mental health domains suggests the importance of stable, supportive housing for emotional well-being.

The high prevalence of psychological distress aligns with studies in Egypt, Pakistan, and other low-to-middle income countries (Fawzy & Hamed, 2017; Islam et al., 2020; Quek et al., 2019). However, your findings show higher rates of anxiety (81.9%) and depression (76.3%) than global averages (Puthran et al., 2016: 28% for depression; Quek et al., 2019: 33.8% for anxiety). These elevated figures may reflect institutional, cultural, or socioeconomic stressors such as academic competition, lack of mental health support, or social stigma surrounding emotional expression.

While your current data summary does not specify breakdowns by gender or lifestyle factors, previous literature consistently highlights gender differences. For example, female students were often found to be at higher risk of anxiety, depression & stress (Amr et al., 2008; Fawzy & Hamed, 2017). Furthermore, factors such as physical inactivity, excessive screen time, rural background, and financial stress have been identified as significant predictors of psychological distress (Islam et al., 2020; Abdel Wahed & Hassan, 2017).

This study underscores the high burden of anxiety, depression & stress among university students, with anxiety being the most prevalent and severe. The findings call for the implementation of targeted mental health interventions, stress-management workshops, academic counseling, and increased access to

psychological services. Universities should prioritize student well-being as part of their academic mission to ensure a healthy learning environment.

Conclusion

This study found that among university students, depression was not significantly predicted by the socio-demographic or behavioral factors examined, suggesting the influence of other unmeasured variables. In contrast, anxiety and stress were associated with environmental and familial factors, including place of birth, living arrangements, parental education, and age. These findings highlight the importance of social context and developmental stage in students' mental health and emphasize the need for interventions addressing living conditions, family-related pressures, and tailored university support systems. Further research is needed to explore additional predictors of depression and understand the mechanisms linking environmental and familial factors to psychological well-being.

Limitations

- i. Cross-sectional design prevents causal inference.
- ii. Moderate sample size ($N=249$) may limit detection of smaller associations.
- iii. Reliance on self-reported behavioral data may introduce bias.
- iv. Important variables such as academic performance, social support, personality traits, and prior mental health history were not included.
- v. Psychological and biological determinants were not assessed.

Recommendations

Future studies should use longitudinal designs with larger, more diverse samples and include qualitative methods to capture students' experiences. Intervention studies targeting modifiable factors like living arrangements and family dynamics could help reduce anxiety and stress. Multidisciplinary approaches combining psychological, social, and biomedical perspectives are recommended for effective prevention and management of mental health issues among university students.

References

1. Vargas-Prada, Sergio, and David Coggon. "Psychological and psychosocial determinants of musculoskeletal pain and associated disability." *Best practice & research Clinical rheumatology* 29, no. 3 (2015): 374-390.
2. World Health Organization (2012). Trends in maternal mortality: 1990 to 2010. WHO, UNICEF, UNFPA and The World Bank.
3. Eisenberg, D., Hunt, J., Speer, N. (2013). Mental health in American colleges and universities: Variation across student subgroups and across campuses. *Journal of Nervous and Mental Disease*, 201(1), 60-67.
4. Saleem, S., Mahmood, Z., Naz, M. (2013). Mental health problems in university students: A prevalence study. *FWU Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(2), 124-130
5. Zada, Shagufta, Yuefen Wang, Muhammad Zada, and Fatima Gul. "Effect of mental health problems on academic performance among university students in Pakistan." *Int. J. Ment. Health Promot* 23 (2021): 395-408.
6. Irfan, M. (2016). Orally disintegrating films: A modern expansion in drug delivery system. *Saudi Pharmaceutical Journal*, 24(5), 537-546.
7. WHO, UNICEF, UNFPA, and The World Bank (2012). Trends in maternal mortality: 1990 to 2010. World Health Organization, UNICEF, UNFPA, and The World Bank
8. Cleary, M., Walter, G., Jackson, D. (2011). Not always smooth sailing: Mental health issues associated with the transition from high school to college. *Issues in Mental Health Nursing*, 32(4), 250-254.
9. Cook, L. J. (2007). Striving to help college students with mental health issues. *Journal of Psychosocial Nursing and Mental Health Services*, 45(4), 40-44. 406 IJMHP, 2021, vol.23, no.3
10. Belch, H. A. (2011). Understanding the experiences of students with psychiatric disabilities: A foundation for creating conditions of support and success. *New Directions for Student Services*, 134(1), 73-94.
11. Kiuhara, S. A., Huefner, D. S. (2008). Students with psychiatric disabilities in higher education settings: The Americans with Disabilities Act and beyond. *Journal of Disability Policy Studies*, 19(2), 103-113.
12. Institute of Health Metrics and Evaluation. Global Health Data Exchange (GHDx), (<https://vizhub.healthdata.org/gbd-results/>, accessed 14 May 2022).
13. Mental Health and COVID-19: Early evidence of the pandemic's impact. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2022.
14. Saravanan, C. and Wilks, R. (2014) Medical Students' Experience of and Reaction to Stress: The Role of Depression and Anxiety. *The Scientific World Journal*, 2014, Article ID 737382. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2014/737382>
15. Wong, J.G.W.S., Cheung, E.P.T., Chan, K.K.C., Kamela, K.M. and Tang, S.W. (2006) Web-Based Survey of Depression, Anxiety and Stress in First-Year Tertiary Education Students in Hong Kong. *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Psychiatry*, 40, 777-782. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/j.1440-1614.2006.01883.x>
16. Saddichha, S. and Christoday, K.R.J. (2010) Prevalence of anxiety, depression & stress among Young Male Adults in India: A Dimensional and Categorical Diagnoses-Based Study. *Journal of Nervous & Mental Disease*, 198, 901-904. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/NMD.0b013e3181fe75dc>
17. Gan, W.Y., Mohd Nasir, M.T., Shariff, Z.M. and Hazizi, A.S. (2011) Disordered Eating Behaviours, Depression, Anxiety and Stress among Malaysian University Students. *College Student Journal*, 45, 296. <http://connection.ebscohost.com/c/articles/61863660/disordered-eating-behaviors-depression-anxiety-stress-among-malaysian-university-students>
18. Al-Ani, Radeef, A.S. and Ghazi, F.G. (2015) Depression, Anxiety and Stress among Undergraduate Science Students in Malaysia. *17th Johor Mental Health Conference*, Malaysia, 17-18 April 2015, Unpublished. <http://irep.iium.edu.my/42809/>
19. Prevalence of Depression among University Students: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis Study
20. Reavley and A. F. Jorm, "Prevention and early intervention to improve mental health in higher education students: a review," *Early*

- Intervention in Psychiatry, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 132-142, 2010.
21. J. M. Castaldelli-Maia, S. S. Martins, D. Bhugra et al., "Doesragging play a role in medical student depression cause oeffect?" *Journal of Affective Disorders*, vol. 139, no. 3, pp. 291-297, 2012.
 22. I. Rivas-Acuña V, García H, Cruz A, et al. Prevalencia de ansiedad y depresión en las personas con Diabetes Mellitus Tipo 2. *Salud en Tabasco*. 2011;17(1-2):30-35.
 23. Bernard JER. Depression: a review of its definition. *MOJ Addict Med Ther*. 2018; 5(1):6-7. DOI: 10.15406/mojamt.2018.05.00082
 24. Prevalence of depression and depressive symptoms among outpatients: a systematic review and meta-analysis
 25. Barlow, D. H. (2002). *Anxiety and its disorders: The nature and treatment of anxiety and panic* (2nd ed.). New York: Guilford Press.
 26. Xi Y. Anxiety: a concept analysis. *Front Nurs*. 2020; 1: 9-12.
 27. De Raeve L, Vasse R, Jansen N, van den Brandt P, Kant I. Mental Health Effects of Changes in Psychosocial Work Characteristics: a Prospective Cohort study, Paper presented at the 13th European Congress of Work and Organizational Psychology, Stockholm, Sweden, May 9-1F2; 2007.
 28. Edwards JA, Webster S, VanLaar D, Eastoln S. Psychometric analysis of the UK Health and Safety Executive's Management Standards work-related stress Indicator Tool. *Work Stress*. 2008;22:96-107.
 29. Tse J, Flin R, Mearns K. Facets of job effort in bus driver health: Deconstructing 'effort' in the EffortReward Imbalance model, *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*. 2010; 12: 48-62.
 30. American Psychiatric Association. *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders* (5th Ed.). Washington, DC, USA: American Psychological Association; 2014.
 31. Rentala S, Nayak RB, Patil SD, Hegde GS, Aladakatti R. Academic stress among Indian adolescent girls. *J Educ Health Promot*. 2019;8:158. https://doi.org/10.4103/jehp.jehp_116_19 Epub 2019/09/24. PubMed PMID: 31544123; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC6745887
 32. Krapić N, Hudek-Knežević J, Kardum I. Stress in adolescence: effects on development. *Int Encycl Soc Behav Sci*. 2015; 23:562-9.
 33. Ratanasiripong P, China T, Toyama S. (2018) Mental Health and Well-Being of University Students in Okinawa. *Educ Res Int* 2018: 4231836.
 34. McCrae RR, John OP. (1992) An introduction to the five-factor model and its applications. *J Pers* 60: 175-215.
 35. Kawase E, Hashimoto K, Sakamoto H, et al. (2008) Variables associated with the need for support in mental health check-up of new undergraduate students. *Psychiat Clin Neurosci* 62: 98-102.
 36. Fortney JC, Curran GM, Hunt JB, et al. (2016) Prevalence of probable mental disorders and help-seeking behaviors among veteran and non-veteran community college students. *Gen Hosp Psychiat* 38: 99-104.
 37. Miller-Graff LE, Howell KH, Martinez-Torteya C, et al. (2015) Typologies of Childhood Exposure to Violence: Associations With College Student Mental Health. *J Am Coll Health* 63: 539-549.
 38. Wanda MC, Carla S. (2013) Stress, Depression, and Anxiety among Undergraduate Nursing Students. *Int J Nurs Educ Scholarship* 10: 255-266.
 39. Ghodasara SL, Davidson MA, Reich MS, et al. (2011) Assessing Student Mental Health at the Vanderbilt University School of Medicine. *Acad Med* 86.
 40. Fares J, Al Tabosh H, Saadeddin Z, et al. (2016) Stress, Burnout and Coping Strategies in Preclinical Medical Students. *North Am J Med Sci* 8: 75-81.
 41. Macaskill A. (2013) The mental health of university students in the United Kingdom. *Brit J Guid Couns* 41: 426-441.
 42. Bovier PA, Chamot E, Perneger TV. (2004) Perceived stress, internal resources, and social support as determinants of mental health among young adults. *Qual Life Res* 13: 161-170.
 43. Lee Kh, Ko Y, Kang Kh, et al. (2012) Mental Health and Coping Strategies among Medical Students. *Korean J Med Educ* 24: 55-63.

44. Ishii T, Tachikawa H, Shiratori Y, et al. (2018) What kinds of factors affect the academic outcomes of university students with mental disorders? A retrospective study based on medical records. *Asian J Psychiat* 32: 67-72.
45. Stallman HM. (2010) Psychological distress in university students: A comparison with general population data. *Aust Psychol* 45: 249-257.
46. Scholz M, Neumann C, Ropohl A, et al. (2016) Risk factors for mental disorders develop early in German students of dentistry. *Ann Anat Anat Anz* 208: 204-207.
47. Schweizer S, Kievit RA, Emery T, et al. (2018) Symptoms of depression in a large healthy population cohort are related to subjective memory complaints and memory performance in negative contexts. *Psychol Med* 48: 104-114.
48. Usher W, Curran C. (2017) Predicting Australia's university students' mental health status. *Health Promot Int* 34: 312-322.
49. Call JB, Shafer K. (2018) Gendered Manifestations of Depression and Help Seeking Among Men. *Am J Mens Health* 12: 41-51.
50. Zeng W, Chen R, Wang X, et al. (2019) Prevalence of mental health problems among medical students in China: A meta-analysis. *Medicine* 98: e15337-e15337.
51. Brockelman KF. (2009) The interrelationship of self-determination, mental illness, and grades among university students. *J Coll Student Dev* 50: 271-286.
52. Roberts SJ, Glod CA, Kim R, et al. (2010) Relationships between aggression, depression, and alcohol, tobacco: Implications for healthcare providers in student health. *J Am Acad Nurse Pract* 22: 369-375.
53. Cai L, Xu F, Cheng Q, et al. (2015) Social Smoking and Mental Health Among Chinese Male College Students. *Am J Health Promot* 31: 226-231.
54. Tountas Y, Dimitrakaki C. (2006) Health education for youth. *Pediatr Endocrinol Rev P* 3: 222-225.
55. Tavolacci MP, Ladner J, Grigioni S, et al. (2013) Prevalence and association of perceived stress, substance use and behavioral addictions: a cross-sectional study among university students in France, 2009-2011. *BMC Public Health* 13: 724.
56. Boulton M, O'Connell KA. (2017) Nursing Students' Perceived Faculty Support, Stress, and Substance Misuse. *J Nurs Educ* 56: 404-411.
57. Jenkins EK, Slemmon A, O'Flynn-Magee K, et al. (2019) Exploring the implications of a self-care assignment to foster undergraduate nursing student mental health: Findings from a survey research study. *Nurs Educ Today* 81: 13-18.
58. Rosenthal SR, Clark MA, Marshall BDL, et al. (2018) Alcohol consequences, not quantity, predict major depression onset among first-year female college students. *Addict Behav* 85: 70-76.
59. Terebessy A, Czeglédi E, Balla BC, et al. (2016) Medical students' health behaviour and self-reported mental health status by their country of origin: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Psychiat* 16: 171.
60. Wallace DD, Boynton MH, Lytle LA. (2017) Multilevel analysis exploring the links between stress, depression, and sleep problems among two-year college students. *J Am Coll Health* 65: 187-196.
61. Hefner J, Eisenberg D. (2009) Social support and mental health among college students. *Am J Orthopsychiat* 79: 491-499.
62. Meng X, Kou C, Shi J, et al. (2011) Susceptibility genes, social environmental risk factors and their interactions in internalizing disorders among mainland Chinese undergraduates. *J Affect Disord* 132: 254-259.
63. Whitton SW, Weitbrecht EM, Kuryluk AD, et al. (2013) Committed Dating Relationships and Mental Health Among College Students. *J Am Coll Health* 61: 176-183.
64. Michalec B, Keyes CLM. (2013) A multidimensional perspective of the mental health of preclinical medical students. *Psychol Health Med* 18: 89-97.
65. McDougall EE, Langille DB, Steenbeek AA, et al. (2016) The Relationship Between Non-Consensual Sex and Risk of Depression in Female Undergraduates at Universities in Maritime Canada. *J Interpers Violence* 34: 4597-4619.

66. Yao B, Han W, Zeng L, et al. (2013) Freshman year mental health symptoms and level of adaptation as predictors of Internet addiction: a retrospective nested case-control study of male Chinese college students. *Psychiat Res* 210: 541-547.
67. Thomas L, Orme E, Kerrigan F. (2020) Student Loneliness: The Role of Social Media Through Life Transitions. *Comput Educ* 146: 103754.
68. Li M, Li WQ, Li LMW. (2019) Sensitive Periods of Moving on Mental Health and Academic Performance Among University Students. *Front Psychol* 10: 1289.
69. Sznitman SR, Reisel L, Romer D. (2011) The Neglected Role of Adolescent Emotional Well-Being in National Educational Achievement: Bridging the Gap Between Education and Mental Health Policies. *J Adolesc Health* 48: 135-142.
70. Vaughn AA, Drake RR, Haydock S. (2016) College student mental health and quality of workplace relationships. *J Am Coll Health* 64: 26-37.
71. Bradley G. (2000) Responding effectively to the mental health needs of international students. *High Educ* 39: 417-433.
72. Miron, Judit, Ximena Goldberg, C. López-Sola, R. Nadal, A. Armario, R. Andero, J. Giraldo, J. Ortiz, N. Cardoner, and D. Palao. "Perceived stress, anxiety and depression among undergraduate students: An online survey study." *Journal of Depression and Anxiety* 8, no. 330 (2019): 2167-1044.
73. Othman, N., Ahmad, F., El Morr, C., & Ritvo, P. (2019). Perceived impact of contextual determinants on depression, anxiety and stress: a survey with university students. *International journal of mental health systems*, 13, 1-9.
74. Wahed, Wafaa Yousif Abdel, and Safaa Khamis Hassan. "Prevalence and associated factors of stress, anxiety and depression among medical Fayoum University students." *Alexandria Journal of medicine* 53, no. 1 (2017): 77-84.
75. Beiter, Rebecca, Ryan Nash, Melissa McCrady, Donna Rhoades, Mallori Linscomb, Molly Clarahan, and Stephen Sammut. "The prevalence and correlates of anxiety, depression & stress in a sample of college students." *Journal of affective disorders* 173 (2015): 90-96.
76. Amir Hamzah, Nurul Syafika, Nik Daliana Nik Farid, Abqariyah Yahya, Caroline Chin, Tin Tin Su, Sanjay Rampal Lekhraj Rampal, and Maznah Dahlui. "The prevalence and associated factors of depression, anxiety and stress of first year undergraduate students in a public higher learning institution in Malaysia." *Journal of Child and Family Studies* 28 (2019): 3545-3557.
77. Bayram, Nuran, and Nazan Bilgel. "The prevalence and socio-demographic correlations of depression, anxiety and stress among a group of university students." *Social psychiatry and psychiatric epidemiology* 43 (2008): 667-672.
78. Teh, Choon Khim, Choon Wei Ngo, Rashidatul Aniyah binti Zulkifli, Rammiya Vellasamy, and Kelvin Suresh. "Depression, anxiety and stress among undergraduate students: a cross sectional study." *Open Journal of Epidemiology* 5, no. 4 (2015): 260-268.
79. Asif, Saba, Azka Mudassar, Talala Zainab Shahzad, Mobeen Raouf, and Tehmina Pervaiz. "Frequency of depression, anxiety and stress among university students." *Pakistan journal of medical sciences* 36, no. 5 (2020): 971.
80. Ramón-Arbués, Enrique, Vicente Gea-Caballero, José Manuel Granada-López, Raúl Juárez-Vela, Begoña Pellicer-García, and Isabel Antón-Solanas. "The prevalence of depression, anxiety and stress and their associated factors in college students." *International journal of environmental research and public health* 17, no. 19 (2020): 7001.
81. Fauzi, Muhammad Faris, Tengku Shahrul Anuar, Lay Kek Teh, Wai Feng Lim, Richard Johari James, Rohana Ahmad, Mawarni Mohamed, Sahol Hamid Abu Bakar, Farida Zuraina Mohd Yusof, and Mohd Zaki Salleh. "Stress, anxiety and depression among a cohort of health sciences undergraduate students: the prevalence and risk factors." *International journal of environmental research and public health* 18, no. 6 (2021): 3269.

82. Blanco, Vanessa, Mar Salmerón, Patricia Otero, and Fernando L. Vázquez. "Symptoms of anxiety, depression & stress and prevalence of major depression and its predictors in female university students." *International journal of environmental research and public health* 18, no. 11 (2021): 5845.
83. Hossain, Md Moyazzem, Md Asraful Alam, and Monirul Hasan Masum. "Prevalence of anxiety, depression, and stress among students of Jahangirnagar University in Bangladesh." *Health science reports* 5, no. 2 (2022): e559.
84. Gabal, H. A., M. M. Wahdan, and D. A. Gamal Eldin. "Prevalence of anxiety, depression and stress among medical students, and associated factors." *Egypt J Occup Med* 46, no. 1 (2022): 55-74.
85. Yu, Yanling, Wangwang Yan, Jiadan Yu, Yangfan Xu, Dan Wang, and Yuling Wang. "Prevalence and associated factors of complains on anxiety, depression & stress in university students: an extensive population-based survey in China." *Frontiers in psychology* 13 (2022): 842378.
86. Karing, Constance. "Prevalence and predictors of anxiety, depression and stress among university students during the period of the first lockdown in Germany." *Journal of affective disorders reports* 5 (2021): 100174.
87. Shamsuddin, Khadijah, Fariza Fadzil, Wan Salwina Wan Ismail, Shamsul Azhar Shah, Khairani Omar, Noor Azimah Muhammad, Aida Jaffar, Aniza Ismail, and Raynuha Mahadevan. "Correlates of depression, anxiety and stress among Malaysian university students." *Asian journal of psychiatry* 6, no. 4 (2013): 318-323.
88. Loviband, S.H., Loviband, P.F., 1995. *Manual for the Depression Anxiety Stress Scales*, second ed. Psychology Foundation, Sydney
89. Antony, M.M., Bieling, P.J., Cox, B.J., Enns, M.W., Swinson, R.P., 1998. Psychometric properties of the 42-item and 21-item versions of the Depression Anxiety Stress Scales in clinical groups and a community sample. *Psychological Assessment* 10, 176-181
90. Shea, T.L., Tennant, A., Pallant, J.F., 2009. Rasch model analysis of the Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scales (DASS). *BMC Psychiatry* 9 (21) <http://www.biomedcentral.com/1471-244X/9/21> (retrieved 24.2.11).
91. Loviband, P.F., 1998. Long-term stability of anxiety, depression & stress syndromes. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology* 107, 520-526.